

Psammobates tentorius verroxii
Bushmanland tent tortoise

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Reptile

Size: maximum 15cm

Distribution:

Bushmanland and Upper Karoo in South Africa, and southern Namibia.

Importance:

The Bushmanland tent tortoise, an important seed disperser for various plant species and endemic to South Africa and Namibia, is arguably one of the most taxonomically confusing and morphologically polymorphic species of Testudines. It is listed as "Near Threatened" by the IUCN and occurs in the Upper Karoo, Bushmanland regions of South Africa, and southern Namibia. It only occurs in the Nama Karoo Biome. Remarkably, no genomic studies have been conducted on any tortoise species in Africa or across the entire Southern Hemisphere.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 97.28 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 7.68 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome Length: 2.24 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 97.6%, Duplicated: 2%]

Assembly N50: 2 312.32 kilobases

Contig number: 10 395

Sample Contributor contact details:

Dr Zhongning Zhao

University of the Free State

orochi19851020@yahoo.com

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